

THE SPIRITUAL JOURNEY OF FORTY-FIVE VASSA: A REFLECTION ON THE BUDDHA'S LIFELONG TEACHING MISSION

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Abstract

This research article states the importance of the forty-five Rain Retreats (Vassa) practiced by the Buddha throughout his teaching efforts for Buddha Sasana. At the first Vassa at Isipatana, the Buddha preached the first Dhammacakkappavattana Sutta, which was the set in motion the Wheel of Dhamma, and moreover, the article traces the spiritual and historical milestones of each Vassa as a manifestation of the Buddha's great compassion and commitment to liberating beings from suffering. This research article finds out the main discourses and important events from the Buddha's missionaries, highlighting how he skilfully used to his teachings to variety of followers and disciples, to establishing a spiritual community rooted in ethical conduct, meditative discipline, and wisdom. The last Vassa of the Buddha, at Kusinārā is given special focus, because it was reflecting on the Buddha's last teachings to his disciples and his peaceful Maha Parinibbāna. Beyond historical events and records, this article offers the reflections on the Vassa as a symbol of spiritual discipline, seasonal renewal, and continuous teaching of the Buddha, moreover, it shows how the Buddha's life, tireless work around these retreats, represents a sacred journey of Dhamma propagation and serves as a guiding model for monastic and lay practitioners alike. The Forty-Five Vassa are not merely chronological markers but embody the full spectrum of the Buddha's spiritual mission, which starting from the first teaching of the Dhamma to the serene conclusion of his Maha Parinibbana.

Key Words: *Vassa, retreat, rainy, journey, Dhamma*

Aim of the Article

The main objectives of this article are to explore and reflect upon the spiritual and historical significance of the Forty-Five Vassa by the Buddha throughout his forty-five-year

tireless missionaries. By examining in every *Vassa*, it was not merely as chronological events but as profound milestones in the Buddha's journey, about this article search to offer a deeper understanding of his unwavering missionaries for the Dhamma and the liberation of all sentient beings.

This article aims to highlight for each *Vassa*, rain retreats, which beginning from the First Sermon at Isipatana to the final attainment of *Parinibbāna* at Kusinārā, served as a structured framework through which the Buddha gradually built the foundations of the Buddhist community, delivered essential discourses, and nurtured the moral and spiritual development of both monastics and lay followers. Other aims were to present the *Vassa* as a practical and symbolic embodiment of discipline, compassion, and wisdom within not only in Theravāda tradition but also for the history of Buddhism. Records by the historical accounts, scriptural references, and thematic reflection, the article intends to inspire both scholars and practitioners to appreciate the *Vassa* not only as a monastic observance but also as a timeless guide for spiritual growth, rooted in the Buddha's compassionate mission to guide others toward enlightenment.

The First Vassa: The Turning of the Wheel of Dhamma

The First *Vassa* of the Buddha, at Isipatana marks the sacred and valuable beginning of his teaching mission. After attaining Enlightenment at Bodh Gaya and inspiring and staying 49 days, he set out to Deer Park to deliver the Dhamma. There, he preached the first sermon of *Dhammacakkappavattana Sutta*, which introducing the core teachings of Buddhism, means the Four Noble Truths and the Middle Path. After hearing this discourse, among the first ascetics, Koṇḍañña attained the first *Sotāpanna*, marking as the birth of the Sangha organization and then, in the *Sasana*, it became completing the Three Jewels, as the Buddha, the Dhamma, and the Sangha. Thus, the First *Vassa* signifies not just a rainy-season retreat but the beginning of a global spiritual tradition, where the Enlightened One became the world's teacher and set the Wheel of Dhamma in motion.

The Middle Years: Expansion and Deepening of the Dhamma

During the middle years of his forty-five-year missionary works, the Buddha focused on the spread of the Dhamma to many places, even reaching individuals from every social group. His inclusive approach was welcoming kings and commoners, monks and householders, men and women even challenged the rigid social hierarchies of ancient India (Great Chronicle 412–414). Between these *Vassa*, the Buddha preached several important

teachings for all. The second important *Sutta* of *Anattalakkhaṇa Sutta*,¹ which introduced the doctrine of non-self (Bodhi, Connected Discourses 901–903), and the *Satipaṭṭhāna Sutta*,² which presented a structured path of mindfulness leading to insight knowledge and wisdom. (Ñānamoli and Bodhi 145–148).

As the organization of Sangha speedy expanded, the Buddha established and lay out the *Vinaya* rules³ to maintain harmony, ethical purity, and discipline among monastics (Vinaya Piṭaka I.45–52). Lay disciples also became increasingly significant through their good deeds of generosity (*dana*) and moral conduct (*Sila*), and that time, completing the Fourfold Assembly of monks, nuns, laymen, and laywomen (Harvey 89–91). Therefore, in the middle Vassas mark a phase of philosophical deepening and institutional growth that ensured the stability and longevity of the Buddhist tradition (Gethin 104–106).

The Final Vassa: The Last Teachings at Kusinārā

The forty-fifth and final *Vassa* of the Buddha's life was observed in Kusinārā, a quiet town in the Malla region of northern India. At eighty years of age, the Buddha's body had become weak, though his mind remained fully clear and compassionate (Great Chronicle 1042–1044). Aware that his Parinibbāna was approaching, he used this last period to deliver essential teachings meant to strengthen and guide the Sangha. These events and instructions are preserved in the *Mahāparinibbāna Sutta*, which records the Buddha's final journey, his last conversations, and the closing guidance he offered to his disciples (Walshe 231–260).

The main aims of this discourse are the teaching on impermanence (*anicca*) and the Buddha always reminds the monks that all conditioned phenomena inevitably decay, culminating in his final words: “*Vayadhammāsankhārā; appamādenasampādettha*”, means “All conditioned things are subject to decay; strive on with diligence” (Dīgha Nikāya 16.6.7). Rather than being a message of sorrow, the Buddha's concluding instruction was one of encouragement, reminding the Sangha that liberation remained possible through continuous, mindful practice (Bodhi, In the Buddha's Words 283–284). He further urged them not to depend on any external authority after his passing, giving the well-known counsel: “*Attadīpāviharatha*”, “Be a lamp unto yourselves,” meaning that the Dhamma should be the

¹The *Anattalakkhaṇa Sutta* means "The Discourse on the Not-Self Characteristic," and it teaches the Buddhist doctrine of **anatta** (non-self).

²The *Satipaṭṭhāna Sutta* means "Discourse on the Foundations of Mindfulness," a key Buddhist text attributed to the Buddha that outlines a path to liberation through sustained awareness.

³Vinaya rules are the ethical and disciplinary guidelines for Buddhist monks and nuns, encompassing the rules for monastic life, conduct, and ordination.

guiding principle for one's own effort (Dīgha Nikāya 16.2.26). Therefore, the Buddha's 45th Vassa served as the last of his forty-five-year missionary works. It became a moment of profound wisdom, compassion, and reassurance, reminding the community that while his physical form would soon lose away, however, the Dhamma would remain as a timeless refuge (Gethin 145–147). The message of Kusinārā affirmed that the path to awakening endures for all who follow it with diligence.

Spiritual Significance of the Forty-Five Vassa

During the Forty-Five *Vassa* by the Buddha, he symbolized far more than a chronological sequence; they represent a sustained spiritual mission grounded in compassion, discipline, and unwavering dedication to the welfare of all beings with variety of teachings. Throughout these forty-five years, the Buddha consistently chose active deals with communities and societies, rather than seclusion, teaching the Dhamma, guiding disciples, and strengthening the Sangha across northern India (Dīgha Nikāya 16; Mingun Sayadaw 345). Buddha's every *Vassa* reflects his commitment to share the path to liberation with great compassion (*Maha Karuna*), patience and wisdom (*Panna*) and served as a structured period for meditation, maintaining morality, and community learning. Between each *Vassa*, *Bhikkhus* and *Bhikkhunis* remained in one place, deepening their practice, cultivating unity in the Sangha, and building strong ties with lay followers (Vinaya Piṭaka, Mahāvagga I.137). For the Buddha, he delivered and teachings the Dhamma, that suited to diverse capacities, embodying both skilful means (*upāya-kosalla*) and the gradual method of instruction (*anupubbikathā*) (Saṃyutta Nikāya 55.7). Each *Vassa* can be viewed as a living expression of the Three Trainings (*Ti-sikkhā*): *Sīla* (morality), *Samādhi* (concentration), and *Paññā* (wisdom). The laid down the *Vinaya* of staying in one place enhanced moral conduct, provided conducive conditions for concentration, and nurtured insight into the nature of reality (Aṅguttara Nikāya 3.88).

Therefore, the essence and important of *Vassa* was not merely a seasonal pause but a sacred period of transformation, where ethical refinement and spiritual wisdom blossomed. By this way, Buddha's Forty-Five *Vassas* form a spiritual blueprint for the Buddhist path to enlightenment, as a testament to steady perseverance, compassionate teaching, and the Buddha's lifelong dedication to ending suffering. Everyone can continue to inspire practitioners to cultivate discipline, wisdom, and compassion in every season of life.

Practical Value in Modern Life

Finally, the Buddha's Forty-Five *Vassas* missionaries, continue to hold practical meaning for modern practitioners, followers, and especially in the way contemporary monks observe the yearly rain retreat. However changing world in present days, Buddhist practice of *Vassa* remains a dedicated period of meditation, study, and disciplined living, reflecting the model established by the Buddha (Vinaya Piṭaka, Mahāvagga I.137). Even today, monks from all the Buddhist countries, still refrain and avoid from travel during the rainy season, using this focused time to inspire insight and ensure the continued transmission and teachings of the Dhamma (Mingun Sayadaw 412). For lay devotees, *Vassa* provides a valuable opportunity for spiritual renewal and making merits. During *Vassa* periods, lay followers were engage more merits like practice in meditation, listen to Dhamma talks, or support the Sangha through generosity as robes, medicine, echoing the Buddha's encouragement for periodic reflection and moral cultivation (Aṅguttara Nikāya 3.88).

In the *Vassa* season allows individuals can do their daily responsibilities, but they should realign their lives with spiritual goals. The Buddha's main aim was marked by steady perseverance and compassionate service, which remains a guiding inspiration for both monks and laypeople. His forty-five years of teaching demonstrate that spiritual progress requires like good morality, compassion, patience, continuous practice, and dedication to the welfare of others (Dīgha Nikāya 16). Thus, the Buddha's Forty-Five *Vassas* stand as a living reminder and teachings, that the path to awakening is a gradual, sustained journey grounded in morality, wisdom and compassion.

Conclusion

The Buddha's Forty-Five *Vassa* and the spiritual journey provide a profound lens through which to understand the depth of his enlightenment and the unwavering dedication he maintained toward liberating beings from suffering. Every *Vassa* showed as a distinct and important chapter in his lifelong teaching with valuable missionaries works, revealing how systematically and compassionately he guided individuals and communities toward the Dhamma, furthermore, from the first turning of the Dhamma Wheel at Isipatana to his final teachings in Kusinārā, these annual retreats were not periods of withdrawal but intentional seasons of reflection, instruction, and spiritual nurturing.

These *Vassas* and Buddha's missionaries shows that, the Buddha's deliberate and adaptive approach to teaching, rooted in morality (*Sila*), compassion (*karuṇā*), wisdom (*paññā*), and tireless effort for developing discipline (*virīya*). Reflecting on the Forty-Five
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Vassa inspires a deeper appreciation for the Buddha's gradual yet steadfast approach to spiritual transformation. His journey and efforts remind us that liberation is not achieved through sudden insight alone, however by the long-term cultivation of disciplined practice, ethical conduct, and mindful awareness. The example which the Buddha gave to us that, encourages all practitioners to embody persistence, humility, and compassion in their own lives. Whether by studying, understanding, practicing meditation in practical, or acts of generosity and service, one can walk to the noble path with the same unwavering dedication. Just as the Buddha provided and supported for forty-five years to sharing and teaching the Dhamma practically, for the welfare of all beings, modern practitioners can commit themselves to a lifelong journey of self-cultivation and contribution to society. In doing so, we honor the legacy of the Buddha and continue the essence of his teaching mission across the seasons of our own lives.

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